

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ORIENTATION AS A PREREQUISITE FOR HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

Chagelishvili A.

*PhD student in Business Administration,
Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi state university,
Georgia,*

ORCID ID 0000-0003-3683-3533

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6826267>

Abstract

Orientation of new employees is an initial activity characteristic of many organizations. Its meaning is not determined by mere awareness. Orientation is the initial process of a number of future issues, including human resource development.

The article discusses the role of orientation in human resource development, emphasizes its importance in the case of both new employees and new managers, and analyzes a number of orientation issues.

This paper based on desk research will be useful for researchers of the above issues and any interested person.

Keywords: Human Resource Development; Orientation; Socialization; Integration.

Human resource development (and not only) begins with employee orientation in the organization. It is a necessary or initial activity that is mostly the responsibility of the employer. Orientation is the process of providing essential information about an organization to new employees [1, p. 238]. Orientation is often perceived as an integration (the later stages of orientation), which refers to the more purposeful process of becoming a full member of a team [2, pp. 78-86]. Organizational socialization is also considered as an established term and synonym of orientation in the academic field [3, p. 234–279]. However, despite the abundance of concepts, even more important is their goal of quickly adapting a new employee to the organization and contributing to the achievement of the goals [4, p. 1].

Until the last decade, scientists viewed the process of orientation within a larger category of socialization, while the direction of human resource management was considered insignificant [4, p. 8]. Nowadays, selecting the best and most potential employee is not a guarantee of perfect performance, because in one way or another, everyone needs orientation. The process of orienting new employees is more than just introducing them to colleagues. That is why, in order to provide basic information and perform the job properly, the functions of human resource management are increased and an orientation and training program is formed [1, pp. 238-241]. From the organization's point of view, a successful new employee orientation results in a high level of job satisfaction and a high degree of job performance, more staff involvement and less outflow, less stressful environment and more career efficiency [4, p. 6]. The awareness and adaptability that accompanies orientation promotes and accelerates the professional development of the employee.

The success of the orientation process by accelerating the processes of socialization and integration makes a great contribution to the attention of the leader and the behavior of colleagues. As a result,

the success of the new employee orientation process is indicated by his involvement in the performance of tasks and social assimilation. The orientation process serves 4 main purposes [1, pp. 238-239]:

1. Make the new employee feel at home and in the team.

2. To provide the new employee with basic information such as, for example, corporate e-mail for the performance of official functions. Mail, personnel policy information, etc. Sh.

3. Show the new employee the organization on a large scale: understand its past, current state, culture and strategic vision for the future.

4. Socialize and adapt the new employee to the culture of the organization.

There are 4 different levels in the orientation process, known as 4C [4, p. 2]:

❖ **Level of compliance:** It is the initial level and is often perceived by organizations as part of a formal orientation. The given level implies familiarity with the rules or regulations related to basic legal and organizational policies.

❖ **Clarification level:** refers to the employee's introduction to the new job and related expectations.

❖ **Culture level:** It is a broad field that includes the introduction of formal and informal organizational norms for the new employee.

❖ **Level of Connections:** Includes social relationships and information networks.

The duration of orientation varies and is individual, however as studies and practice show, the process takes about 90 days. To achieve a successful orientation, researchers identify 4 key levers related to the business role and the social environment [4, pp. 1, 4]: 1) The more professionally confident a new employee is, the more motivated he or she is and the more successful and fast his or her orientation process is [5, pp. 211-225]; 2) Like the previous factor, the clearer his/her role is for the new employee, the more active he/she is in the orientation process [6, pp. 309-

318]; 3) A prerequisite for successful orientation is also social integration in the business environment, with the involvement of a new employee, the activity of colleagues or the human resources department [7, pp. 1149-1160]; 4) Understanding organizational culture and adapting to it is the 4th factor in the success of the orientation process. Understanding the organization's policies, goals, values and the unique language of the firm is an important lever for employee adaptation [8, pp. 730-743].

Distinguish between formal and informal orientation. In the informal orientation process, the new employee receives information independently of the organizational plan, while formal orientation involves the introduction of a set of coordinated policies and procedures [4, p. 2]. One such formal orientation tool is a written orientation plan, which is a formal support document for a new employee, a kind of map outlining specific deadlines, goals, responsibilities. Numerous employees of the organization take part in its creation [9].

Technologies are actively used to simplify the orientation process. In many organizations, special online training introduces new mission, policies, and procedures to new employees. A similar way is the existence of an orientation portal, where information is provided through multimedia, and employees can be introduced through relevant profiles [1, p. 239]. The international seismic technology company "ION Geophysical" uses such an online orientation portal called "Red Carpet". The existence of an online orientation platform in this case is justified and flexible, as the company integrates human resources in 5 countries [10, pp. 75-78]. Some employers use a system of QR codes for "orientation stops", where various text or multimedia files generated as a result of their scanning receive information about a specific service [11].

New employees often make mistakes during the orientation phase and it is quite difficult to understand their reactions or attitudes. That is why it is important for the management to pay proper attention to establishing feedback and providing appropriate assistance. During the orientation, the new employee may facilitate the feedback himself / herself and try to obtain or respond to information, which is mainly reflected in his / her proactive behavior, asking questions and other expressions of interest [12, pp. 707-721]. On the first working day, it is important for colleagues to be aware of the arrival of a new employee and to be actively involved in building social relationships. Initially, the HR specialist implements the new employee by providing information such as work schedule and staffing benefits. Then, already the immediate supervisor or curator goes on to explain the peculiarities of the functioning of a particular service, getting to know colleagues, presenting the workplace and trying to ease the inconvenience of the first day. In the beginning, it is necessary to provide the new employee with information about personnel policy, internal regulations or other basic issues, be it in print or digital format [1, pp. 238-239].

It should be noted that managers also need guidance, which should include getting to know the organization's operational plan and key areas of business, key employees and their careers, key partners and other stakeholders [2] [1, p. 239]. The orientation of new managers differs from the standard of employee orientation by several factors: Managers have more relationships with the business community, such as the organization's stakeholders; They are often faced with unique and complex issues; The new leaders are mainly cited to support specific strategic initiatives that may require a change in the status quo rather than an adaptation to it [13, pp. 165-178].

Organizations know that quick orientation of new leaders is important as it will ultimately affect the work of the lower echelons as well [14, p. 62-72]. Studies show that the success of the process of socializing new recruits in the future significantly determines their attitudes, quality of work and, in general, the issue of staying in the organization in the future [12, p. 707-721].

Many organizations are positive about hiring a new manager, however, along with a number of disadvantages, problems such as delays in orientation, efforts spent on integration, the problem of "falling out of bed", etc. should be analyzed [2, pp. 78-86]. According to a global online survey conducted in 2013 by global management consulting and management company Egon Zehnder, which surveyed more than 500 new managers, their main obstacles were identified. 69% of the respondents named orientation problems as the main reasons for failure, in particular, little knowledge about the work and functioning of the organization [15].

Thus, the role of orientation is fundamental for the further development of the new employee, and even more crucial in the case of hiring new managers. Because of this importance, it is not enough for organizations to simply pay attention and provide information to new employees. It is necessary to have a pre-designed and sophisticated orientation program, according to which valuable information will be provided and appropriate action will be taken at each stage.

References:

1. Dessler G., Human resource management, 16th Ed., New York: Pearson, 2020.
2. Byford M., Watkins M. D. & Triantogiannis L., Onboarding Isn't Enough, Harvard Business Review, no. May-June, pp. 78-86, 1 May 2017.
3. Saks A.M. & Ashforth B. E., Organizational Socialization: Making Sense of the Past and Present as a Prologue for the Future, Journal of Vocational Behavior, vol. 51, no. 2, p. 234-279, October 1997.
4. Bauer T.N., Onboarding New Employees: Maximizing Success, SHRM Foundation (Society for Human Resource Management), 2010.
5. Saks A., Longitudinal field investigation of the moderating and mediating effects of self-efficacy on the relationship between training and newcomer adjustment, Journal of Applied Psychology, vol. 80, no. 2, pp. 211-225, 1995.

6. Feldman D. C., The Multiple Socialization of Organization Members, *The Academy of Management Review*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 309-318, 1981.
7. Morrison E. W., Newcomers' Relationships: The Role of Social Network Ties during Socialization, *The Academy of Management Journal*, vol. 45, no. 6, pp. 1149-1160, 2002.
8. Chao G. T., O'Leary-Kelly A. M., Wolf S. & Klein H. J., Organizational Socialization: Its Content and Consequences, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 79, no. 5, pp. 730-743, 1994.
9. Bauer T. N. & Elder E., Onboarding newcomers into an organization, in 58th Annual Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) Conference & Exposition, Washington, D. C, 2006.
10. Arnold J. T., Ramping Up Onboarding, *HR Magazine*, pp. 75-78, May 2010.
11. Price K., QR Codes for Trainers, Alexandria, United States: American Society for Training and Development, 2013.
12. Bauer T. N., Bodner T., Erdogan B., Truxillo D. M. & Tucker J. S., Newcomer adjustment during organizational socialization: A meta-analytic review of antecedents, outcomes, and methods, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 92, no. 3, p. 707-721, 2007.
13. De Meuse D., Gaeddert D. & Guangrong D., Onboarding externally hired executives: Avoiding derailment – accelerating contribution, *Journal of Management & Organization*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 165-178, March 2011.
14. Velsor E. V. & Leslie J. B., Why Executives Derail: Perspectives across Time and Cultures, *The Academy of Management Executive* (1993-2005), vol. 9, no. 4, p. 62-72, 1995.
15. Egon Zehnder, egonzehnder, Egon Zehnder, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://www.egonzehnder.com/what-we-do/leadership-advisory/insights/12th-international-executive-panel-leaders-in-transition>. [Accessed 18 November 2021].